

Fit for Purpose: Strategies for Effective Implementation of Regulations

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abstract

This article considers how organisations should respond to new or changed regulations. Based on an examination of regulations in Australia, three features are identified that provide insights into the appropriate implementation focus: the mandatory nature of regulations, their complexity and duration. A strategic response framework using these features is presented to guide the choice of an approach that is 'fit for purpose' by targeting efforts and resources to achieve the intended outcome of the regulation. This also provides a rationale and value proposition when discussing the implementation approach with the business. Recommendations about the activities for each approach are provided.

Introduction

The person tasked with the implementation of new or changed regulations often meets with resistance from the business. The reasons for this resistance may be concerns about the costs or resources required, lack of clarity about what is required or doubts about the intended benefits. As a result of this resistance, the push from the business is often to do what they must to comply with the regulatory requirements so they can get on with the 'real work'. If doing more than the minimum is suggested, or implemented, the business will often criticise the approach as over-engineered. Yet concerns have been raised that implementation of regulations has been only partially successful in achieving the intended benefits, particularly in the financial services sector (Business Council of Australia, 2005; Wagner and Dittmar, 2006; Regulation Taskforce, 2006; Dalton, 2007).

On the one hand this may indicate that a minimalist approach may be insufficient to achieve the intent of regulations. This is a concern particularly with the move to more principles-based regulations where the 'how to' is not provided yet organisations are held accountable for achieving the outcome or intent (Deighton-Smith, 2006; Financial Services Authority, 2007; Trowbridge, 2007; Mullins, 2008). On the other hand there are a wide variety of types of regulations requiring different responses (Australian Legal Information Institute, 2008) and not all will necessarily move to principles-based. Therefore, while a focus on meeting the compliance requirements may be adequate to deliver the intent of

some regulations, for others doing extra may be more appropriate. This article explores how regulations and the challenges for their implementation can be differentiated in the Australian context. Based on these insights, a strategic response framework is presented that can be used to guide decisions about selecting an appropriate approach to implementing different types of regulations in organisations.

The nature of regulations

Regulations are a form of secondary legislation supporting the implementation of laws (Curtin University, 2008; Parliament of Australia, 2008). They provide the detailed rules about the requirements that must be followed, the penalties for non-compliance and how decisions can be appealed. For instance, the various food regulations support the state and federal food acts to ensure that food is safe for human consumption by regulating, amongst other things, how food must be handled. What is interesting from a change perspective is the mandatory nature of regulations (Donselaar, 2007; Hackman, 2007). Generally, when an organisation decides to implement a change initiative there is a voluntary aspect to it, meaning that they can choose how much or how little is implemented. The management can even stop or limit the implementation if it does not work or the situation changes. However this is not the case for regulations.

For regulatory change, if an organisation wants to continue in the industry, they will have to comply.

Amendments can be made to the regulations that do not work as expected but they are rarely stopped or revoked. Resistance is also an issue when introducing regulations often due to the cynicism about benefits (Business Council of Australia, 2005), and will be high whether the regulations are being increased, decreased or simply changed (Banks 2005). Clearly an appropriate response is to do at least the minimum to comply. However the question still remains as to when it might be appropriate to do more and how much to do.

One feature that has received significant attention in Australia recently is the level of complexity for organisations when implementing regulations (Murray, 2007; Mullins, 2008). This complexity is created through the types of processes that need to be changed or created and the number of stakeholders involved or impacted. Complexity is further increased when the intended outcomes are unclear, evolving or contentious. A review of regulations in 2006 (Regulation Taskforce, 2006) highlighted this burden on organisations and also provided an insight into differing levels of complexity for different types of regulations.

For instance, in the case of the recent Financial Services Reforms for General Insurers (FSR) there was some lack of clarity about how the regulations would operate and organisations could choose the form of advice model they used (Business Council of Australia, 2005). Many different stakeholders were involved in a sequential implementation chain (Hackman, 2007) including the government, regulator, organisation, employees, customers and the wider community. Customers presented a particular challenge as they were required to take more decision making responsibility about purchasing insurance (Hackman, 2006). The impact of each type of stakeholder varied, particularly the differences for large, medium and small organisations. Resistance to this regulation was also high because the intended outcomes, while being articulated in the legislation, were still unclear. Organisations implementing FSR voiced doubts about whether the intended benefits, as they understood them, could be achieved (Business Council of Australia, 2005).

However not all regulations are this complex. For instance, regulations requiring car manufacturers to fit seat belts in new cars are, in comparison to FSR, less complex (Department of Infrastructure, Transport, Regional Development and Local Government, 2008). There are clear 'dos and don'ts' about the processes, who was involved is clear and the outcome measurable. Persuading people to use the seat belts is of course another issue! It could therefore be argued that a different response may be required dependent on the complexity of the regulation.

It does not necessarily follow that a regulation that was comparatively less complex would only require a

minimalist approach to be effective. In fact, the opposite could apply due to the importance of the intent. For instance, wearing hearing protection at work to prevent hearing loss would seem straightforward. Yet there is still a high level of hearing loss reported in Australia (Safety Solutions, 2006). It is clearly not enough to issue the equipment, run training, then tell people to wear it. More action is required from the employer to ensure employees wear the hearing protection equipment correctly. The difference would appear to be where there is a need for sustained behaviour change. In other words, the new behaviours need to be incorporated into the culture of 'how we do things around here' (Schein, 1992; Dalton 2007).

This leads to consideration of whether there is a time element that could also be useful in determining an appropriate implementation response. There are differences in the duration of regulations ranging from a day or less to ones that are implemented for the long term or until the law is next changed. For instance, FSR was implemented to continue and as such required a more permanent change in behaviour for the people in the organisation. This would take more effort because experience has shown that just telling people to change may not be effective for sustained behaviour change (Beer, Eisenstat and Spector, 1990; 2000; Kotter and Cohen, 2002). It would follow that telling people to 'just comply' may also not be effective in the longer term. Additionally, it requires leaders to support a response to change behaviours (Dalton, 2007) and not be dismissive of the effort required.

In contrast, a focus on meeting the minimum compliance requirements may be the right approach for regulations that are brought in for a short time, especially if there is a crisis. For instance, regulation to manage the equine flu outbreak in Australia in 2007 was implemented in this mode which was appropriate in view of the crisis facing the racing industry (Department of Primary Industry, 2008). In saying this, it is recognised that education programs to prevent such outbreaks occurring again would, however, take more thought and education of stakeholders. This would require an approach promoting more sustained behaviour change potentially relating to a longer term regulation supporting the same law.

In summary, regulations are a mandatory form of change and therefore organisations must at a minimum comply if they want to continue operating in the industry. The level of complexity of the regulation in terms of process, stakeholders and intended outcomes provides some insights into what more than the minimum is required for a particular regulation to be successful. The duration of the regulation sharpens this insight by providing a calibration of whether the change in behaviours by people in the organisation needs to be more immediate or

penalties for non adherence to stop people reverting to old behaviours. Clarity change levers explain what behaviours need to change and involve activities such as training and communication over a period of time appropriate for the type of change. Pull change levers encourage people to change their behaviour. Activities would include managers and leaders role modelling the right behaviour and articulation of the benefits for adopting new behaviours to various stakeholders and the people themselves to promote engagement with the change initiatives. Although the emphasis may differ for different types of change, effective change programs contain elements of all three change

sustained over the longer time. Based on this discussion, combining the levels of complexity and duration of regulations could provide insights into an appropriate implementation response that is 'fit for purpose'.

Strategic response framework

Figure 1 shows how complexity and duration can be combined to describe four different responses to implementing regulations. The horizontal continuum is complexity. All regulations by their nature have some complexity so this is a relative rather than an absolute measure with the centre point indicating a medium level of complexity. The vertical continuum is duration with timelines for regulations ranging from a day or less for temporary situation to regulations with no defined end date. The mid point for this continuum would be about one year because a regulation in force for two or more years would be similar to the behaviour change challenge for a regulation with no end date. The approaches are described in terms of whether they are combinations of directive (just do it); procedural (do it this way); educative (this is how); and encouraging (this is why). These descriptions indicate the focus for an appropriate approach, bearing in mind that there is always a minimum requirement to comply.

In the following review of each Quadrant, an explanation of the approach is provided together with an example of a regulation that would fit into the Quadrant. Observations about implementation activities are described using a change lever model (Hackman, 2005). This model comprises three types of change levers. Push change levers institutionalise the change through, for instance, clearly aligned policies, revised practices and

levers. The examples of activities for each change lever provided above will be used in the discussion about the Quadrants. For more details about this change lever model and suggestions about other activities see Hackman (2005).

Quadrant 1: Lower complexity – shorter term

Regulations that would fit into this quadrant have clear processes especially about the 'dos and don'ts', it is clear who should be involved and how they are impacted and there is a clearly understood outcome that is typically not contentious. They are time bounded operating for less than a year. An example of this type of regulation would be one to address a crisis such as management of equine flu outbreak where the spread needed to be stopped quickly (see Department of Primary Industry, 2008). No differentiation was made between organisations or people involved. Everyone, from large training operations to individual owners, had to comply. The key to success in stopping the spread was consistency and timeliness of response.

The appropriate organisation response to use in this circumstance is to focus on compliance and meeting the requirements, a more minimalist approach. So the ideal focus for implementation of regulations in this Quadrant can be described as directive (just do it) and procedural (do it this way). In organisations, the activities would primarily be push change levers and include clearly aligned policies and practices with consequences for non adherence. However, there would be aspects of clarity change levers including training and communication. Time would be against long-term education programs however some training would need to occur so people knew how

to follow the compliance requirements in case there is another outbreak of equine flu. From a pull change lever perspective managers would need to role model the right behaviours.

Quadrant 2: Lower complexity – longer term

Regulations that would fit into this quadrant have clear processes especially, about the 'dos and don'ts'—it is clear who should be involved and how they are impacted and there is a clearly understood outcome that is typically not contentious. However, they are in place continuously and therefore there is a duration aspect with a need for sustained or permanent behaviour change. An example of this type of regulation would be rules about importing used machinery into Australia (Australian Quarantine and Inspection Service, 2008). As with Quadrant 1, no differentiation is made between organisations or people involved. Everyone, from large machinery companies to individual owners, has to comply and only import machinery that is 'clean as new' as defined in the regulation.

The appropriate approach to use is to educate people so they build up knowledge about how to comply, be kept up to date and ensure that new employees are aware of the requirement. This education would need to be ongoing to ensure that people do not become complacent. The ideal focus for implementation of regulations in this quadrant can be described as directive (just do it) and educative (this is how). In organisations, activities would primarily be a combination of push change levers with clearly aligned policies and practices and clarity change levers taking time to provide education about how to comply. There would be some pull change levers to explain the benefits of using the right behaviours and, again, managers leading by example.

Quadrant 3: Higher complexity – longer term

Regulations that would fit into this quadrant have more complex processes with some lack of clarity about the 'dos and don'ts', there may be choices for organisations to make about how they implement the regulations, many stakeholders would be involved and it would not always be clear how they would be impacted. The benefits or outcomes may not be well understood, may still be emerging and may even be contentious. As with Quadrant 2, they are in place continuously and therefore there is a duration aspect with a need for sustained or permanent behaviour change. An example of this type of regulation would be FSR (Australian Securities and Investments Commission, 2008). This regulation presented challenges for organisations for developing and implementing new processes and training their employees in new processes in such a way that they change their behaviour permanently. Just telling people to comply would be unlikely to develop their skill to operate in an environment that is to a degree ambiguous.

So the ideal focus for implementation of regulation in this Quadrant can be described as encouraging (this is why) and educative (this is how). Being the most comprehensive approach, activities in organisations would include a balance of all types of change levers. There would be push change levers with clearly aligned policies and procedures, clarity change levers with training and communication over a longer period of time, and pull change levers to communicate benefits to encourage people to engage, plus there would be leadership by role modelling the right behaviours. A smaller organisation without a lot of resources might not take on a large scale change program but also may not do the minimum to comply if this is not sufficient to achieve the intent of the regulations. With insights into the appropriate approach, they may choose elements to do themselves such as communication to their workforce and use of industry bodies to provide assistance with other implementation aspects to gain scale and therefore cost effectiveness (such as use of common education programs).

Quadrant 4: Higher complexity – shorter term

Regulations that would fit into this quadrant have more complex processes with some lack of clarity about the 'dos and don'ts'. There may be choices for organisations to make about how they implement the regulations, many stakeholders would be involved and it would not always be clear how they would be impacted. Similar to Quadrant 3, the benefits or outcomes may not be well understood, may still be emerging and may even be contentious. However, as with Quadrant 1, regulations are time bounded and operating for less than a year. An example of this type of regulation is one put in place to address a need surrounding an event such as meetings of Asia Pacific Economic Co-operation (APEC). The purpose is to enable the event to run smoothly and without incident. For instance, during the APEC meeting in Sydney in 2007, not only were there security provisions but also organisations in the Central Business District (CBD) had to implement a one day public holiday for CBD-based staff (Attorney-General's Department, 2008). This may not have been contentious for people who gained a holiday but it may have been for people who missed out! Organisations were apparently not pleased about the potential impact on performance and profitability.

Nevertheless, organisations had to plan for the disruption to their businesses, manage the expectations of all staff and also ensure their staff knew what to do when they were in the CBD on the days they attended work. So the ideal focus for implementation of regulations in this Quadrant can be described as encouraging (this is why) and directive (do it this way). In organisations, activities would focus on the push change levers with clearly aligned policies and procedures and the pull change levers explaining the benefits to encourage people to

comply. Clarity change levers would mainly comprise explaining to people what is expected of them through communications such as email and team briefings.

Using the framework

This framework presents a way of classifying regulations so that an appropriate response can be identified. However there are a few more layers involved to understand how to use this framework to fullest effect. Firstly, several regulations can support implementation of the same law but they may be in different Quadrants indicating different responses are appropriate. For instance, Quadrant 1 lower complexity, shorter-term regulations can operate along side longer-term regulations supporting the implementation of the same law. When the immediate need is over, the education component to prevent further occurrences would reside in a different quadrant indicating a different approach as appropriate. In the case of equine flu this would indicate a need to change from being procedural and directive to be more educative. So while there may be a specific implementation plan for one regulation, managers would benefit from understanding the bigger picture and how

appropriate approach to the business. This can prevent problems caused by using the same response for all regulations or using an approach more suitable for a regulation in a different Quadrant. For example, a Quadrant 1 approach suitable for lower complexity – shorter term regulations is unlikely to be successful for the implementation of Quadrant 3 higher complexity – longer-term regulations. A more comprehensive change program would be required that includes activities to promote sustained behaviour change. Equally, if a more comprehensive change program suitable for Quadrant 3 regulations is used for implementation of Quadrant 1 regulations then the approach is likely to be not only considered over-engineered but will also not meet the immediacy of the need.

There does not need to be a high profile change program consuming valuable time and resources for implementation of every regulation. However, the implementation does need to include all change levers in the appropriate balance for the regulation to increase the likelihood of success. The key is selecting the approach that is ‘fit for purpose’, developing the value proposition for the business and implementing the appropriate blend of activities over the right timescale.

Conclusion

This article examined the challenge of regulatory change to develop a strategic decision making framework to guide selection of an approach to the implementation of new or changed regulations. This framework enables the person tasked with the implementation

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the implementation plan may need to evolve to respond to related but different regulations.

Secondly, there may be different aspects within the same regulation requiring different responses. The framework can be used to plot these to understand the appropriate combination of responses. For instance, different workforce segments may need different approaches depending on their involvement in the implementation of the regulations. Frontline employees selling insurance to customers under the FSR regulations would need more comprehensive education compared to back office employees who have no contact with customers but need to be aware not to provide advice. Again, understanding and planning for the bigger picture can be of benefit here, especially in targeting resources appropriately.

Thirdly, the framework can be used to explain the

of regulations, whatever the size of their organisation, to assess the regulatory challenge strategically and make an informed choice about an approach that is ‘fit for purpose’ in order to develop an appropriate implementation plan. It also provides a rationale and basis for a value proposition for the person to use when discussing the approach and implementation plan with the business. Management of expectations becomes easier when there is a sound rationale for the approach chosen with a clear and appropriate implementation plan. The outcome will be to streamline and target efforts and resources in the right place, demonstrate real value for the business and address the intent of the regulation thereby maximising effectiveness. ❖

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